

**Românitate în epoca globalizării:
continuitate și identitate la est de Prut**

**Romanian Identity in the Age of Globalization:
Continuity and Identity East of the Prut**

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Cultural Identity of the Bessarabian Village Today

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Abstract. *The political, socio-economic, and cultural events of the past three decades have significantly shaped the evolutionary trajectory of the Republic of Moldova, particularly that of the rural community. During this period, it has undergone a challenging process of redefinition, marked by demographic, occupational, and value transformations. This study provides documented information on the demographic, cultural, and spiritual crisis affecting Moldovan villages, including ethnically mixed ones. The findings reveal that although the rural community faces image-related challenges, it continues to serve as a loyal guardian of traditional cultural values by preserving and transmitting both tangible and intangible cultural heritage, as well as passing on crafts, traditions, and folk customs to younger generations.*

Keywords: *cultural identity; village; commune; crisis.*

1. Introduction

The political, socio-economic, and cultural events of the past three decades have shaped the evolutionary trajectory of the Republic of Moldova. Radical changes in society began in 1989, when the national liberation movement contributed to the rebirth of society through culture. On August 27, 1991, the Republic of Moldova declared itself an independent country—an historic event preceded by numerous rallies, protest marches, and strikes, with protesters demanding official recognition of Romanian linguistic and cultural identity, the return to the Latin alphabet, and the declaration of the Romanian language as the state language.

Several major events followed, determining the country's European future, including Moldova's admission to the Council of Europe (1995), the entry into force of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with the EU (1998), the granting of full membership in the World Trade Organization (2001), the accession to the Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe (2001), Moldova's inclusion in the Eastern Partnership, and the signing of the Association Agreement with the European Union (2014), along with dozens of other intergovernmental treaties and conventions.

These events have particularly affected the rural community, which, over the last three decades, has undergone a difficult process of redefinition, experiencing demographic, occupational, and value transformations.

In this study, we aim to provide documented information on the cultural and spiritual life of Moldovan villages, including ethnically mixed ones. The research was preceded by dialectological expeditions organized within the project The Romanian Language and Folklore in the Process of Consolidating the Statehood of the Republic of Moldova. A total of 24 rural localities were visited (from the network of The Romanian Linguistic Atlas by Regions: Bessarabia, Northern Bukovina, Transnistria),

characterized by significant historical and cultural heritage, differing by function and structure (Pavel, V., Corcimari, V., Spînu, S. et al., 2023).

2. Theoretical Framework. Overview of the Visited Rural Localities

The oldest localities included in the network of surveyed points were Nișcani in the Călărași district (first documented in 1432 under the name Heghetiș), the villages Țăra (dated 1437) and Cenușa (attested in a document issued by Stephen the Great on May 11, 1479, under the name Borodniceni) in the Florești district, and Saharna in the Rezina district (recorded on January 24, 1495, when Stephen the Great confirmed through a charter the division of property among the heirs of Sima Rugină). Among the localities of more recent origin are Nădușita, Drochia district (first documented in 1845), Văleni, Cahul district (founded in 1808 by 59 Romanian peasant families), Zaim, Căușeni district (mentioned in written sources beginning with the 15th–16th centuries), and Ochiul Alb, Drochia district (recorded in 1788).

Among the smallest villages visited (with up to 500 inhabitants) were Țăra (Florești district), Saharna (Rezina district), and Roșietici (Florești district); among those with 500–1,500 inhabitants were Ordășei (Telenești district), Stoicani (Soroca district), and Cenușa (Florești district); and among the larger ones (1,500–3,000 inhabitants) were Chiștelnița (Telenești district), Ochiul Alb (Drochia district), and Mândrești (Telenești district).

Economically, all these villages are predominantly agricultural, focusing on cereals, fruit growing, vegetable farming, or viticulture. However, their development levels are uneven. Peri-urban villages such as Trebujeni (Orhei district), Cișmea (Orhei district), and Chiștelnița (Telenești district) maintain permanent relations with nearby towns and stand out through an improved quality of life, an effective educational system, and active political and socio-cultural engagement. In contrast, more remote rural localities such as Ciobalaccia (Cantemir district), Zaim (Căușeni district), and Trifăuți (Soroca district) continue to face economic, sociocultural, and political difficulties.

Socioeconomic and political realities have led to demographic decline. According to statistical data, in 2004 the population of the Republic of Moldova was 3,604,000 people (1,310,000 living in rural areas and 2,294,000 in urban areas); in 2014 it was 2,998,235 people (1,918,054 in rural areas and 995,227 in urban areas); and in 2024 it reached 2,401,200 people (based on estimated usual residence) (National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova, 2024).

A negative demographic situation was observed in villages located farther from urban centers. The most unfavorable demographic profiles were recorded in the localities of Țăra (Florești district), Saharna (Rezina district), Roșietici (Florești district), Stoicani (Soroca district), and Cenușa (Florești district). For example, in Stoicani commune there were 1,550 inhabitants in 2004, 1,202 in 2014, and 763 in 2024 (National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova).

The demographic situation in the Republic of Moldova has been shaped by two major factors: demographic modernization - characterized by changes in population behavior (declining fertility, postponement of childbirth to more mature ages, diversification of family models, etc.) - and a prolonged socioeconomic and political

crisis. One manifestation of the socioeconomic crisis is the mass migration of the working-age population and the persistently high mortality rate among adults (Paladi, 2015, p. 59). Consequently, the village ceases to represent the main source of demographic potential, a reality that affects not only economic development but also the socio-cultural evolution of the country.

The demographic decline is also influenced by globalization, which has changed the rural community's perception of true life values, weakened the cultural identity of the traditional village, and significantly affected its architectural tradition. The localities have lost much of their authenticity and traditionalism, being subjected to multiple transformations characteristic of the modern era. Although construction and ornamentation techniques for houses and homesteads have evolved over time, most villages have failed to preserve a distinct, uniform, and traditional style. However, the appearance of the northern villages still differs from those in the south, a tendency preserved since the early 20th century:

"In the wooded regions of the Hotin, Soroca, Orhei, and Chișinău counties, the yards are fenced with woven wicker enclosures. Every peasant house is shaded by a small orchard, while on the surrounding hills and slopes the villagers' vineyards bask in the sun; in the southern counties, where forests are absent and wood is expensive, houses lack fences and have no other outbuildings except corn cribs, alongside which stand stacks of hay and straw, and here and there a well with a lever, called cocostârc (stork)" (Arbore, 1899, p. 247).

3. Theoretical Analysis. The Cultural Identity of the Contemporary Bessarabian Village

The lifestyle in Bessarabian villages remains deeply rooted in tradition. Traditional crafts such as wood carving, egg decoration, pottery, carpet weaving, embroidery, and icon painting continue to be practiced and promoted. Valuable handmade artifacts created by locals are preserved in village museums in Ciobalaccia (Cantemir district), Gribova (Drochia district), Văleni (Cahul district), and Hoginești (Călărași district). The inhabitants contribute to enriching these collections through donations of works made from willow twigs, plant fibers, and ceramics.

A key component of the cultural identity of rural areas is the traditional costume. Throughout history, every nation has identified itself through a distinct style of clothing. As Leroi-Gourhan (1983, p. 167) notes, "Clothing has, above all, an ethnic value. Belonging to a group is first marked by one's appearance." In the localities visited, before the annexation of Bessarabia by the Russian Empire in 1812, the national costume was worn daily. Later, it was gradually replaced by urban clothing. Today, interest in traditional attire has significantly declined.

To nurture respect for national values and promote cultural heritage, houses of culture in rural areas organize artistic and cultural events such as folk music and dance concerts, storytelling evenings, and traditional gatherings. These initiatives not only preserve traditions but also enhance the touristic potential of rural areas. In Zaim (Căușeni district) and Țâra (Florești district), libraries have been designed in a rustic style, reminding visitors of the villagers' historical and cultural past.

In this context, the cultural and spiritual life of ethnically mixed villages is also of great interest. The Republic of Moldova is a multiethnic, multicultural, and multiconfessional state, where several ethnic groups coexist within the same localities. A relevant example is Ivancea (Orhei district), first documented in 1501. Archaeological evidence shows that the area has been inhabited for approximately 3,500 years B.C., with successive settlements being destroyed by fires and invasions. During 1000–600 B.C., several small villages appeared, which were later destroyed by Germanic Bastarnae tribes. After the Roman conquest of Dacia, new communities emerged but were later devastated by the Huns. Between 700 and 1300 A.D., several other villages arose, and during 1300–1700 A.D., nine hamlets were recorded in historical sources. All these medieval settlements were burned and abandoned. The surviving inhabitants founded a new settlement on the site of the present-day village. Historical records frequently mention Ivancea and its people. By 1940, much of the native population had left the area, leaving behind only 1,396 residents, primarily Ukrainians (Eșanu & Grossu, 2012, p. 517).

In 2003, Ivancea gained the status of a commune, comprising the villages Ivancea, Brănești, and Furceni. According to census data, in 2004 the commune had 5,904 inhabitants, while in 2014 the population dropped to 3,624, of whom 50.47% identified as Moldovans, 43.59% as Ukrainians, 4.40% as Russians, 0.51% as Gagauz, and 0.09% as other ethnicities. In 2024, the total number of inhabitants remains 3,624 (National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova, 2024).

To ensure peaceful coexistence and social cohesion, a favorable multicultural environment has been created in the locality. There are no significant communication barriers between representatives of different ethnicities caused by stereotypes, prejudice, discrimination, ethnocentrism, or xenophobia. Locals are aware of and promote their own cultural values while acknowledging the similarities and differences of the cultures they interact with. The formation of intercultural competences—cognitive, affective, and behavioral—is one of the main educational objectives pursued by the local school. The Ivancea Gymnasium has about 105 students and 19 teachers.

At the same time, traditional national values continue to be promoted through cultural events. Since 2014, every year at the end of August, Ivancea hosts the Cucuteni Festival, where some of the most beautiful prehistoric painted ceramics in Europe are exhibited. As noted by *Voyages Moldavie*, “Witness to the birth of true art and the discovery of the Cucuteni civilization, this festival is a unique event that brings together the best ceramic artists and painters from different countries, inspired by the mysteries of the ancient Cucuteni–Tripolye civilization.” This event attracts cultural figures and promotes intercultural dialogue, creativity, and reflection within the community.

The church in Ivancea, designed by the academician architect A. Șciusev, is also a valuable historical monument. Today, it serves as a unifying spiritual center for both the titular population and minority groups. The shared faith in Christian values and the moral continuity of traditions have fostered a sincere interreligious dialogue within this ethnically diverse community.

4. Conclusions

Therefore, although the rural community faces image problems, it remains a faithful promoter of traditional cultural values by preserving and perpetuating the intangible and tangible heritage, transmitting crafts, traditions and customs to new generations. Significant in this context is the statement of Lucian Blaga: "We are and will always be a nation of peasants. Therefore, our destiny as a nation, as a cultural power, depends on the amount of pure gold that is in the soul of the peasant - the creator and preserver of popular culture, a generating, blessed and fruitful center".

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